

Studies in Tetraphenylmethane Dyes. Part II.

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Sen and Banerjee (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 77) prepared a few derivatives by condensing rosaniline base with aromatic amino and hydroxy compounds all of which were found to possess satisfactory dyeing properties and for which tetraphenylmethane structures were assumed.

In continuation of that work a few more compounds have now been obtained by condensing (i) crystal violet base and (ii) malachite green base with aromatic amino and hydroxy compounds. Tetraphenylmethane structure has also been ascribed to the compounds described in this paper. But this requires to be proved later on by further work.

The method adopted is the same as that of Sen and Banerjee (*loc. cit.*) viz., by heating crystal violet base or malachite green base with a suitable mono or dihydroxy or aminobenzene at about 160-80° for 6-8 hours using fused anhydrous sodium acetate as the condensing agent, the yields of the products varying from 60 to 80% of theory.

The reaction which takes place may be represented as follows:

where X = OH or NH₂ or NMe₂, etc.

The hydrogen atom *para* to X reacts with the OH of the carbinol as usual.

Though these compounds cannot be represented by any quinonoid configuration in the ordinary manner, they are as good dyes as the triphenylmethane dyes; such extraordinary quinonoid structure as

is, however, conceivable. Such alternative method of condensation involving atmospheric oxidation as

does not appear very likely to take place.

The compounds derived from crystal violet may be regarded as the crystal violet base in which the carbinol 'OH' has been replaced by a phenyl residue with or without any auxochromic group and their colour is generally similar to that of crystal violet more or less modified by the additional auxochromic groups, as will be evident from the table.

In the malachite green series analogous results are obtained, the shades on silk and wool of the condensation products being influenced exactly in the same way as in the case of crystal violet.

In this connection it is interesting to note that when the condensation of crystal violet or malachite green base with salicylic acid or *o*-cresotinic acid is attempted, carbon dioxide is eliminated and the product is identical with the product obtained from phenol or *o*-cresol respectively.

As recorded by Sen and Banerjee (*loc. cit.*) it has also been found that these tetraphenylmethane derivatives undergo a marked change

of colour in acid solution in strong sulphuric acid or hydrochloric acid exhibiting from yellow to red shade which on much dilution changes from light reddish-violet to deep bluish-violet in the crystal violet series and from light greenish-blue to deep emerald green in the case of the malachite green series. No such phenomenon is, however, observed in the case of the acetic acid solution.

EXPERIMENTAL.

General method of preparation and purification.—1 Mol. of the base (C.V. or M. G.*) was mixed with $1\frac{1}{2}$ mol. of the other component (aniline, phenol, etc.) and the mixture heated on the oil-bath till a homogeneous solution was obtained. Some fused sodium acetate was then added, the mixture well stirred, the temperature gradually raised and maintained at 160-180°. After 1 hour some more of sodium acetate was added and the heating continued for 6-8 hours with frequent stirring. When the reaction was over the excess of the second component was removed by (i) steam distillation (aniline, dimethylaniline, anisole, resorcin dimethylether), (ii) ether extraction (anisole, resorcin dimethylether) (in the C. V. series only), (iii) treatment with caustic soda (phenol, o-cresol), (iv) washing with water (resorcinol). Any excess of the base was removed by treating carefully with water slightly acidulated with hydrochloric acid in which the base (C. V. or M. G.) is very easily soluble while the product is not so readily soluble. The residue was then thoroughly washed, dried, and then treated with solvents.

Crystal Violet Series.

Hexamethyltetraminotetraphenylmethane, prepared from crystal violet base and aniline, separates from a mixture of alcohol and chloroform as a blue powder melting at 115-16°. It is sparingly soluble in alcohol and toluene, soluble in chloroform, acetone, benzene, carbon disulphide; insoluble in ether, petroleum ether, benzene. (Found: N, 12.32. $C_{31}H_{36}N_4$ requires N, 12.1 per cent).

The *acetyl* derivative crystallised from alcohol as a reddish violet powder, m. p. 66-68°. (Found: N, 11.3. $C_{33}H_{38}ON_4$ requires N, 11.1 per cent).

* C. V. = Crystal violet base. M. G. = Malachite green base.

p-Hexamethyltriaminotriphenylmethylbenzene-azo- β -naphthylamine was prepared by coupling the diazotised amine with β -naphthylamine. It separates from petroleum ether (b. p. 95°) as an orange-red powder, m. p. $116-17^{\circ}$. (Found: N, 13.9. $C_{41}H_{42}N_6$ requires N, 13.6 per cent).

sym-Octamethyltetraminotetraphenylmethane, prepared from the base and dimethylaniline, separated from alcohol and chloroform as a bluish violet powder melting at 102.4° . It is sparingly soluble in alcohol, benzene, ether, toluene; readily soluble in chloroform, acetone, carbon disulphide and insoluble in petroleum ether. (Found: N, 11.61. $C_{33}H_{40}N_4$ requires N 11.4 per cent).

p-Hydroxyhexamethyltriaminotetraphenylmethane, prepared from the base and phenol, was crystallised from boiling absolute alcohol as a reddish-violet powder, m.p. 102° . It is sparingly soluble in alcohol, toluene, benzene; readily soluble in chloroform and acetone and insoluble in ether, petroleum ether and carbon disulphide. (Found: N, 9.4. $C_{31}H_{35}ON_3$ requires N, 9.03 per cent).

The *acetyl* derivative crystallised from alcohol as a light blue powder, m. p. $84-85^{\circ}$. (Found: N, 8.34. $C_{33}H_{37}O_2N_2$ requires N, 8.28 per cent).

2:4-Dihydroxyhexamethyltriaminotetraphenylmethane, prepared from the base and resorcinol, crystallised from a boiling solution of alcohol and acetone as a violet powder melting above 270° . It is sparingly soluble in alcohol, chloroform, readily soluble in acetone and insoluble in benzene, ether, petroleum ether, carbon disulphide and toluene. (Found: N, 8.75. $C_{31}H_{35}O_2N_3$ requires N, 8.73 per cent).

The *benzoyl* derivative crystallised from benzene as a slate coloured powder, m.p. $117-19^{\circ}$. (Found: N, 6.24. $C_{45}H_{43}O_4N_3$ requires N, 6.1 per cent).

p-Methoxyhexamethyltriaminotetraphenylmethane, prepared from the base and anisole, crystallised from acetone as a sapphire blue powder, m.p. $140-44^{\circ}$. It is sparingly soluble in alcohol, acetone; moderately soluble in chloroform, benzene, toluene, carbon disulphide; insoluble in ether and petroleum ether. (Found: N, 8.93. $C_{32}H_{37}ON_3$ requires N, 8.77 per cent).

2:4-Dimethoxyhexamethyltriaminotetraphenylmethane, prepared from the base and resorcin dimethylether, crystallised from alcohol as a bluish-violet powder, m.p. 122° . It is sparingly soluble in alcohol, toluene; soluble in chloroform, acetone, benzene and carbon

disulphide; insoluble in ether and petroleum ether. (Found: N, 8.4. $C_{33}H_{39}O_2N_3$ requires N, 8.25 per cent).

3-Methyl-4-oxyhexamethyltriaminotetraphenylmethane, prepared from the base and *o*-cresol, crystallised from boiling absolute alcohol as a bluish-violet powder, m. p. 95°. It is sparingly soluble in alcohol, benzene, toluene and carbon disulphide; readily soluble in chloroform, acetone; insoluble in ether and petroleum ether. (Found: N, 9.11. $C_{32}H_{37}ON_3$ requires N, 8.77 per cent).

The *acetyl* derivative crystallised from alcohol as a reddish-violet powder, m. p. 64-65°. (Found: N, 8.42. $C_{33}H_{39}O_2N_3$ requires N, 8.06 per cent).

Malachite Green Series.

Tetramethyltriaminotetraphenylmethane, prepared from malachite green base and aniline, crystallised from alcohol as a greenish-blue powder, m. p. 102°. It is sparingly soluble in alcohol, benzene, toluene and carbon disulphide; readily soluble in chloroform and acetone. (Found: N, 10.1. $C_{29}H_{31}N_3$ requires N, 9.98 per cent).

The *acetyl* derivative crystallised from alcohol as a buff coloured powder, m. p. 90°. (Found: N, 9.2. $C_{31}H_{33}ON_3$ requires N, 9.07 per cent).

p-Tetramethyldiaminotriphenylmethylbenzeneazo- β -naphthylamine, prepared by coupling the diazotised amine with β -naphthylamine, crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 75-95°) as a yellowish-brown powder, m. p. 160-62°. (Found: N, 12.4. $C_{39}H_{37}N_5$ requires N, 12.17 per cent).

Hexamethyltriaminotetraphenylmethane, prepared from the base and dimethylaniline, crystallised from alcohol as a bluish-green powder, m. p. 107-10°. It is sparingly soluble in alcohol, toluene and carbon disulphide; readily soluble in chloroform, acetone and benzene. (Found: N, 9.57. $C_{31}H_{35}N_3$ requires N, 9.35 per cent).

p-Hydroxytetramethyldiaminotetraphenylmethane, prepared from the base and phenol, crystallised from a warm mixture of alcohol and acetone as a light blue powder, m.p. 75°. It is sparingly soluble in alcohol, toluene; readily soluble in acetone, benzene, carbon disulphide and chloroform. (Found: N, 6.63. $C_{29}H_{30}ON_2$ requires N, 6.61 per cent).

The *acetyl* derivative crystallised from alcohol as a brownish-yellow powder, m. p. 93-95°. (Found: N, 6.24. $C_{31}H_{32}O_2N_2$ requires N, 6.03 per cent).

2: 4-Dioxytetramethyl-diaminotetraphenylmethane, prepared from the base and resorcinol, crystallised from a boiling mixture of alcohol and chloroform as a greenish ash-coloured powder, m. p. 124-26°. It is sparingly soluble in alcohol, benzene, ether and toluene and readily soluble in chloroform and acetone. (Found: N, 6.53. $C_{29}H_{30}O_2N_2$ requires N, 6.39 per cent).

The benzoyl derivative crystallised from benzene as a dark grey powder, m. p. 113°. (Found: N, 4.6. $C_{43}H_{38}O_4N_2$ requires N, 4.33 per cent).

p-Methoxytetramethyl-diaminotetraphenylmethane, prepared from the base and anisole, crystallised by adding benzene to a boiling methyl alcoholic solution as a bluish-green powder, m. p. 90-95°. It is soluble on warming in benzene, carbon tetrachloride; readily soluble in alcohol, ether, ethyl acetate, acetone, chloroform and pyridine. (Found: N, 6.71. $C_{30}H_{32}ON_2$ requires N, 6.42 per cent).

2:4-Dimethoxytetramethyl-diaminotetraphenylmethane, prepared from the base and resorcin dimethylether, crystallised from alcohol as a dark grey powder, m. p. 85-87°. It is sparingly soluble in alcohol and ether; readily soluble in chloroform, acetone, benzene, toluene and carbon disulphide. (Found: N, 6.27. $C_{31}H_{34}O_2N_2$ requires N, 6.01 per cent).

3-Methyl-4-oxytetramethyl-diaminotetraphenylmethane, prepared from the base and o-cresol, crystallised from benzene and petroleum ether as a pea-green powder melting at 113-15°. It is sparingly soluble in alcohol, acetone, benzene; readily soluble in alcohol, chloroform, toluene and carbon disulphide. (Found: N, 6.54. $C_{30}H_{32}ON^2$ requires N, 6.42 per cent).

The acetyl derivative crystallised from alcohol as an almond brown powder, m. p. 90-91°. (Found: N, 5.99. $C_{32}H_{34}O_2N_2$ requires N, 5.86 per cent).

TABLE.

$$V = (C_6H_4 \cdot NMe_2)_3 \equiv C - . \quad C. V. = \text{Crystal violet base.}$$

Compound.	Method of preparation.	Colour and dyeing properties on silk and wool.	Remarks.
$V-C_6H_4 \cdot NH_2$ (I)	C. V. + aniline	Bluer shade than C. V.	
$V-C_6H_4 \cdot NHCOMe$	Acetylation of (I)	Lighter shade than (I) (redder)	Acetylation lightens the shade.
$V-C_6H_4 \cdot N = N - C_{10}H_6 \cdot NH_2$	Azo compound of (I) with β -naphthylamine	Golden yellow shade	
$V-C_6H_4 \cdot NMe_2$	C. V. + dimethylaniline	Blue	
$V-C_6H_4 \cdot OH$ (II)	C. V. + phenol	Lighter shade than (I)	Methylation lightens the shade (cf. Sen and Banerjee, <i>loc. cit.</i>).
$V-C_6H_4 \cdot OCOCH_3$	Acetylation of (II)	Blue. Much lighter than (I)	Weaker auxochrome OH replacing the stronger auxochrome NH_2 lightens the shade.
$V-C_6H_3(OH)_2$	C. V. + resorcin	Less bluer than (II)	
$V-C_6H_4 \cdot OMe$	C. V. + anisole	Redder than (II)	
$V-C_6H_3(OMe)_2$	C. V. + resorcin dimethyl ether	Same shade as C. V.	No dyeing property as there is no auxochrome in the phenyl residue, no effect of Me group.
$V-C_6H_3(OH)(Me)$ (III)	C. V. + o-cresol	Same shade as (II)	
$V-C_6H_3(OCOMe)(Me)$	Acetylation of (III)	Less blue than (III)	

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